

Supporting Information

Unveiling dissolution kinetics of CuO nanofertilizer using bio-based ionic liquids envisaging controlled use efficiency for sustainable agriculture

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Section I: Detailed experimental description

Synthesis of PGR-ILs

PGR-ILs were synthesized by neutralizing cholinium carbonate with the appropriate acid, a well-established protocol that has been described in detail previously.^{1,2} The choline cation was chosen because it is widely distributed in plant tissues and the anions are biomolecules that regulate plant growth. Briefly, the acids were suspended in ethanol and added dropwise to an excess of base under vigorous stirring room conditions, producing carbon dioxide and water. The mixture was allowed to stand for 24 hours with stirring and the lid open to remove the carbon dioxide formed. Unreacted starting materials were removed by liquid-liquid extraction with ethyl acetate. To reduce water content and volatile impurities, ILs were purified under vacuum (1 Pa) at room temperature with stirring for at least 48 h. The structure of the precursors and synthesized compounds was confirmed by ¹H NMR (Nuclear Magnetic Resonance) spectra, and the synthesized ILs exhibited a 1:1 acid-base ratio along with a high degree of purity (Figure S1).

Materials characterization

The PGR-ILs were characterized by ¹H NMR in a Bruker Avance 300 at 75 MHz using deuterated water (D₂O) as solvent. Further manipulations on the purely synthesized compounds were performed in a glovebox with dry argon to avoid water absorption. CuO nanoparticles were characterized before and after dissolution experiments and contact with ILs using scanning Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and powder X-ray diffraction (p-XRD). TEM analyses were performed using a Hitachi HD-2700 microscope at 200 kV and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) using a Bruker Nano GmbH microscope. NPs were suspended in water and dispersed by sonication, and TEM grids were prepared by immersion. p-XRD measurements were performed at room conditions using an Empyrean X-ray diffractometer from PANalytical B.V. operating with a Cu anode ($K\alpha_1 = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$; $K\alpha_2 = 1.5444 \text{ \AA}$) and equipped with a PIXcel^{1D} detector. Diffraction data were collected in continuous mode in the 2θ range of $10\text{-}70^\circ$ in steps of 0.04° and with a time per step of 295 s. Diffraction-free sample holders were used in the measurements. The pH was measured using a Mettler Toledo™ S470 pH benchtop meter. Cu ion concentration in aqueous solution containing PGR-ILs was quantified using a Picofox S2 (Bruker Nano, USA) total reflectance X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (TXRF) with a molybdenum X-ray source (X-ray tube voltage: 50 kV and current: 600 μA).

Experimental protocol to study the dissolution kinetics of Cu ions from CuO in PGR-ILs

The release of copper ions from CuO was studied in ultrapure water and in the aqueous solutions containing [Cho][Asc], [Cho][IAA], [Cho][IBA], [Cho][GA₃], and [Cho][Sal] according to literature procedures.^{3,4} Due to the expected low dissolution of copper ions, an approach adapted from previous work was implemented here,^{5,6} in which dialysis tubing cellulose membranes act as 'filters' for particles of undissolved copper oxide. The dialysis membranes were previously humidified for at least 3 h with running water and subjected to pretreatment according to the manufacturer's instructions.⁷ Then, one end of the dialysis tubing with a length of about 10 cm was closed with a double tight knot and the membranes were filled with the desired aqueous medium (water or water + PGR-IL). Copper oxide in excess was carefully added to the tubing attached to the plastic cover. The initial concentration of copper oxide and PGR-ILs used in each experiment are listed in [Table S1](#). The system tubes + membranes containing 40 mL of ultrapure water and CuO + PGR-ILs were ultrasonicated for 2 min to desegregate the particles and then shaken at 200 rpm and 25°C in a Carousel 12 Plus reaction station. Aqueous samples of approximately 1 g were taken from the outside of the membrane after 1 h, 6 h, 12 h, 24 h, 72 h, and 168 h, diluted in 1 wt.% polyvinyl alcohol, and spiked with a known concentration of yttrium standard (1000 mg/L Certipur® standard, Sigma-Aldrich). 10 µL of each sample was then placed on a previously treated carrier (containing 10 µL of silicon in isopropanol solution) and dried on a hot plate at 353 K. Metal quantification was performed using a TXRF spectrophotometer with a molybdenum X-ray source (X-ray tube voltage: 50 kV and current: 600 µA). At least three independent measurements were made at each time point and in each solution, and the acquisition time was 500 seconds. The pH of the suspensions was measured before the experiment (in aqueous solutions of PGR-ILs) and after the end of the experiment (aqueous solutions of PGR-ILs and dissolved copper ions). Solutions containing [Cho][Asc] were evaluated by ¹H NMR after 7 days, with the water peak suppressed by Bruker NMR software.

Evaluation of the impact of Cu ion + PGR-ILs as foliar spray on tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*)

Preparation of nanoformulations

To evaluate the effect on tobacco plant growth, the following treatments were prepared: (1) H₂O (control), (2) H₂O + CuO, (3) H₂O + [Cho][Acs], (4) H₂O + [Cho][IBA], (5) H₂O + [Cho][GA₃], (6) H₂O + [Cho][Sal], (7) H₂O + [Cho][Asc] + CuO, (8) H₂O + [Cho][IBA] + CuO, (9) H₂O + [Cho][GA₃] + CuO, and (10) H₂O + [Cho][Sal] + CuO. The suspensions containing copper oxide and/or ionic liquids were prepared by mixing the desired amounts ([Table S2](#)) with ultrapure water in Falcon tubes with a volume of 50 mL, allowed to stir for 6 days at room conditions, and filtered using 0.02 µm syringe filter units. For the subsequent greenhouse experiments, the filtration process is essential to separate the

dissolved Cu ions from the undissolved copper in the solution, since the goal is to determine the effect of the copper ions dissolved with the PGR-ILs. The formulations containing [Cho][IBA] were diluted 1000-fold after the filtration procedure. The potential degradation of PGR-ILs in the nanoformulations was evaluated after 3 months by ^1H NMR following the procedure described in the previous section.

Greenhouse experiments

To test the efficiency of the nanoformulations based on Cu ions + PGR-ILs, tobacco seeds (*N. tabacum* L. cv Petit Havana) were germinated under *in vitro* conditions as described in Štefanić et al.⁸ with minor modifications. Briefly, seeds were surface sterilized with 70% (v/v) ethanol for 60 seconds, washed 3x with sterile deionized H₂O, and soaked in 50% (v/v) sodium hypochlorite with an active chlorine concentration of 1.5% for 6 minutes before being rinsed 3x in sterile deionized H₂O. Seeds were then germinated on half-strength Murashige and Skoog (MS)⁹ culture medium supplemented with 15 g L⁻¹ sucrose. Tobacco seedlings were then planted in pots (3 seedlings per pot) with sterile peat substrate and maintained under greenhouse conditions (16/8 light/dark cycle, light intensity 90 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 70% RH, and temperature 24°C). The experiment was conducted in a randomized complete block design (RCBD) with three replicates. Seedlings were allowed to grow for up to 19 days and sprayed with different Cu ions + PGR-ILs -based nanoformulations four times at one-week intervals until the end of the experiment. Each pot received approximately 1 g of the nanoformulations per treatment, as calculated from the mass difference before and after spraying. The control was treated with ultrapure water without any nanoformulations. Prior to application, plants were checked for uniformity, well-developed shoots, and differentiated leaves. Pots were watered to field capacity (3.5 ml g⁻¹ substrate) throughout the experiment.

Study of plant growth

The effect of nanoformulations on plants was evaluated 1 week after each foliar application by observing plant phenotype, which included plant height above ground, number of true leaves, and leaf area. Data were collected at time points t-0, t-7, t-14, t-21, t-28, and t-35 from the first day of foliar application. The designations t-0, t-7,..., t-35 are used to indicate the time point, where t-0 corresponds to the day of the first spray, and t-35 the last day of treatment. At the end of the experiment (8 weeks after sowing), the roots and shoots were harvested. The roots and shoots were rinsed with tap water followed by distilled water. After removing the excess water with filter paper, the fresh weight was measured. Plant samples were dried at 65 °C in a forced-air oven for 48 h to determine dry biomass yield. Phenotypic data were collected in triplicate for each treatment. Images

of plant shoots and roots were also taken to qualitatively evaluate the effects of the different treatments.

Chlorophyll index and gas exchange parameters

Chlorophyll index in leaves was measured nondestructively using a portable SPAD-502Plus Chlorophyll Meter (Konica Minolta GmbH). Leaf photosynthetic efficiency was measured on individual plants per treatment and sampling point, for all treatments at three time points (t-7, t-14, t-21), and at each foliar spray. Photosynthetic parameters were measured in triplicate for each plant considering actively growing leaves, with 9 measurements per treatment. Gas exchange parameters such as net photosynthetic rate P_N ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), transpiration T_r ($\text{mmol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), conductance Cond ($\text{mol H}_2\text{O m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$), and intercellular CO_2 concentration C_i ($\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) were measured using a LI-6400XT Portable Photosynthesis System (LI-COR Biosciences) on a leaf in the same position on each plant (one plant per treatment). Measurements were made under artificial light conditions in the chamber at an intensity of $750 \mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $400 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1} \text{ CO}_2$ with a flux of $200 \mu\text{mol s}^{-1}$, and 50-65% RH. The instrument was recalibrated after each measurement of 15 samples to obtain stable readings.

Copper mapping

After harvesting, a fresh leaf was selected at the same position on each plant (1 per treatment, second true leaf from the base/bottom of the plant), and preserved according to the herbarium method. After complete drying, a rectangular area of about 0.5-1 cm x 1 cm of each leaf was fixed on the double-sided tape before ablation. An inductively coupled single quadrupole plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) instrument 7700x (Agilent, Santa Clara, CA, USA) and a laser ablation (LA) system LSX-500 (CETAC Technologies, Omaha, NE, USA) were used for copper mapping. The LA-ICP-MS was optimized prior to analysis by ablation of certified glass NIST 610 reference material to achieve the required sensitivity and oxide and double charged ion content < 0.5%. Laser ablation parameters were selected using a single digit method while a leaf sample was ablated. The resulting instrumental parameters of LA-ICP-MS are as follows: laser energy 50%, laser scanning speed $400 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$, laser spot size $200 \mu\text{m}$, distance between lines $400 \mu\text{m}$, laser shot frequency 4 Hz, sample gas (argon) 1 mL min^{-1} , plasma power 1550 W, and acquisition time per mass per reading 50 ms. The isotopes observed were ^{13}C and ^{63}Cu . The background signal measured before the start of ablation was subtracted. The ^{63}Cu signal was normalized to the ^{13}C signal to minimize signal fluctuations caused by variable sample thickness and instrumental drift. The double-sided tape was checked for copper content, that was found to be negligible (normalized signal $\text{Cu/C} < 0.1$). Data were processed using MS Excel 2021, and maps were generated using ImaJar software developed in-house (Robin Schmid, University of Münster).

Elemental analysis and copper content of leaves

Dried root and shoot tissues were ground into powder using a homogenizer (Taurus, 25 790 Barcelona, Spain) and passed through a 1 mm sieve to obtain a fine powder. Elemental content, including C, H, N, and S, was measured in the ground powder using a CHNS analyzer (Leco Truspec-Micro CHNS 630-200-200). Root and shoot tissue carbon content was used in conjunction with dry biomass yield to calculate the extent of CO₂ sequestration. Similarly, N content was used to calculate crude protein content, by %N x 6.25.¹⁰ In addition, Cu content of shoots and roots was quantified using TXRF as described above.

Statistical analysis

The data obtained from pH, phenotypic, and physiological studies was statistically analyzed using paired sample T-test in OriginPro 2023 software (OriginLab Corporation, United States). The paired sample T-test revealed significant differences (with the level of significance set at $p < 0.05$) between treated plants and the control for various parameters, including leaf area, chlorophyll index, gas exchange parameters, dry biomass content, CO₂ sequestration, and crude protein content.

Section II: Precursors and synthesized ionic liquids characterization

^1H NMR

Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectra of the pure precursors and of the synthesized ionic liquids.

Section III: Suspensions preparation

Table S1. Initial ionic liquid and copper oxide concentrations of the suspensions prepared for the ion release profile experiments.

Suspensions	IL / mM	CuO / ppm
H ₂ O + CuO	-	110
H ₂ O + [Cho][Asc] + CuO	10.3	112
H ₂ O + [Cho][IAA] + CuO	10.1	102
H ₂ O + [Cho][IBA] + CuO	8.4	100
H ₂ O + [Cho][GA ₃] + CuO	4.3	112
H ₂ O + [Cho][Sal] + CuO	9.4	107

Table S2. Initial ionic liquid and copper oxide concentrations of the suspensions prepared for the plant application experiments.

Suspensions	IL / mM	CuO / ppm
H ₂ O + [Cho][Asc]	9.8	-
H ₂ O + [Cho][IBA]	8.7	-
H ₂ O + [Cho][GA ₃]	5.0	-
H ₂ O + [Cho][Sal]	10.7	-
H ₂ O + CuO	-	112
H ₂ O + [Cho][Asc] + CuO	9.8	179
H ₂ O + [Cho][IBA] + CuO	8.5	175
H ₂ O + [Cho][GA ₃] + CuO	4.8	92
H ₂ O + [Cho][Sal] + CuO	10.7	116

Section IV: Ion release profiles and NPs characterization

Table S3. Dissolution of copper ions in different mediums as a function of time.

Suspensions	t / h	Copper ions concentration / ppb					
		1	6	12	24	72	168
H ₂ O + CuO		7 ± 2	16 ± 2	23 ± 1	36 ± 1	-	61 ± 1
H ₂ O + [Cho][Asc] + CuO		115 ± 8	716 ± 18	1176 ± 19	1491 ± 40	4310 ± 142	36369 ± 1238
H ₂ O + [Cho][IAA] + CuO		5 ± 1	9 ± 1	17 ± 2	24 ± 2	34 ± 1	55 ± 3
H ₂ O + [Cho][IBA] + CuO		4 ± 1	6 ± 1	11 ± 1	19 ± 1	33 ± 1	58 ± 5
H ₂ O + [Cho][GA ₃] + CuO		4 ± 2	7 ± 1	13 ± 1	17 ± 2	28 ± 1	65 ± 4
H ₂ O + [Cho][Sal] + CuO		138 ± 5	528 ± 20	1304 ± 44	2579 ± 124	6343 ± 360	12459 ± 427

Table S4. D-spacing values from the crystalline structure of copper oxide obtained from HR-TEM, and directly measured with the ImageJ software.

	Length / nm			Length / nm	
	CuO	CuO + [Cho][Sal]		CuO	CuO + [Cho][Sal]
1	0.229	0.335	16	0.313	0.273
2	0.236	0.285	17	0.304	0.248
3	0.229	0.310	18	0.304	0.260
4	0.296	0.273	19	0.304	0.211
5	0.244	0.310	20	0.288	0.248
6	0.278	0.285	21	0.252	0.273
7	0.280	0.273	22	0.323	0.261
8	0.325	0.223	23	0.261	0.248
9	0.313	0.273	24	0.270	0.298
10	0.252	0.323	25	0.261	0.260
11	0.261	0.298	Mean	0.276	0.272
12	0.227	0.248	SD	0.032	0.029
13	0.252	0.260	Min	0.227	0.211
14	0.261	0.248	Max	0.325	0.335
15	0.323	0.273			

Figure S2. High-resolution TEM images showing lattice spacing of CuO nanoparticles before the ion release profile experiments (left panel), and of non-dissolved CuO after the dissolution kinetics in [Cho][Sal] (right panel).

Figure S3. EDS spectra of: a) CuO before the ion release profile experiments; and non-dissolved CuO after dissolution kinetics in: b) [Cho][Asc]-based medium, c) [Cho][GA₃]-based medium, d) [Cho][Sal]-based medium.

Figure S4. ^1H NMR spectra of pure [Cho][Asc], and aqueous [Cho][Asc] and [Cho][Asc]+CuO, after 7 days kinetics. The ^1H NMR spectra of the water phase was evaluated by suppressing the water peak.

Section V: Plant application

Figure S5. ^1H NMR spectra of pure ILs and their mixtures with water and CuO, prepared following the procedure described in section 2.5.1 in the experimental section of the manuscript, after 3 months. The ^1H NMR spectra of the water phase was evaluated by suppressing the water peak.

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